

Vyttila 3, a new rice variety for acid saline areas

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Vyttila 3 has been released for acid saline areas of Kerala. The Vyttila 1/Taichung Native 1 cross yields 200 kg/ha more than improved pureline selection Vyttila 1.

Vyttila 3, with 115 d duration, is

Performance of Vyttila 3 in farmers' fields, Kerala, India.

Location	Yield (t/ha)	
	Vyttila 1	Vyttila 3
Parur	0.9	1.3
Vyttila	3.6	3.8
Maradu	2.4	2.4
Panangad	3.7	4.0
Chellanam	4.5	5.0
Kandekadavu	4.3	4.1
Kannamali	4.5	4.9
Mean	3.4	3.6

suitable for May-Jun to Sep-Oct (pokkali season) cultivation. It is 166 cm tall with 3.6 t/ha average yield potential and 5 t/ha maximum yield potential (see table). Kernels are red with good cooking quality; protein content is 7.8%.

The variety is photoperiod insensitive and tolerant of major diseases and most insect pests (except stem borer, leafroller, and rice bug). □

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

TEMPERATURE TOLERANCE

Chhomro — a promising cold-tolerant traditional rice variety for rainfed wetlands in western hills in Nepal

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No improved rice varieties have yet been identified for temperate regions, particularly for elevations above 1,500 m. We evaluated 57 local varieties and 367 exotic materials during 1985-86. Local rices were collected from the altitude range 1,000-2,300 m in the western hills. Major sources of exotic materials were the International Rice Cold Tolerance Nursery (IRCTN), the National Cold Tolerance Rice Nursery (NCTRN), and an initial evaluation trial (IET) carried out in collaboration with the National Rice Improvement Programme (NRIP), Parwanipur.

Cold tolerance screening nurseries were established at LAC (1,500 m). Mean air temperatures during early seedling growth (Jun-Jul) were 16.2-17.1 °C minimum and 22.6-22.8 °C maximum. During ripening (Oct-Nov), minimum temperature was 9.9-15.2 °C and maximum was 16.7-20.1 °C. Maximum water temperature was 20.1 °C in Jul and 14.0 °C in Oct. Cold tolerance of local and exotic varieties was measured by leaf discoloration at seedling stage, spikelet sterility, and grain yield.

Table 1. Comparative performance of selected cold-tolerant rice varieties identified in different nurseries. LAC, 1985-86.

Trial or nursery	Best yielding varieties	Grain yield (t/ha) at 12% moisture content	Sterility ^d (%)	Cold injury at seedling stage ^e (1-9 scale)
Farmers' field, 1985 (n= 13)	Chhomro local	5.3	0	1
	Banahu local	5	.05	3
	Ghara local	3.4	15	3
NCTRN, 1985 (n = 30)	Laisika-F	4.2	20	3
	WR10072-79-1-2-3	2.4	25	3
	NR10068-60-3-2	2.2	25	4
IRCTN, 1985 (n = 184)	Laisika-I	5.1	5	3
	K39-96-1-1-1-2	4.9	5	4
NCTRN, 1986 (n = 22)	Chhomro local	4.8	0	1
	NR10073-167-3-1-3	4.1	30	4
	Phalame	3.4	60	4
LRCTN ^a , 1986 (n = 52)	Chhomro local	5.0	2	1
	Seto Bhakunde	3.9	2	2
	Kalo Patle	3.2	1	2
	Raksali	3.1	5	3
PON ^b , 1986 (n = 50)	Banahu local	4.1	6	2
	Chhomro local	4.0	5	1
	Raksali	2.8	10	3
SFT ^c , 1986 (n = 36)	Chhomro local	4.1	0	1

^a Local Rice Cold Tolerance Nursery. ^b Preliminary Observation Nursery. ^c Spacing × Fertility Trial on Chhomro local. ^d Spikelet sterility was estimated by eye and by grasping the panicle. ^e Measured according to the procedures mentioned in the IRRI *Standard evaluation system for rice* scale.

Table 2. Comparative performance of 2 best cold-tolerant local varieties of rice at an altitude of 1500 m.^a LAC, 1985-86.

Variety	Plant stand/m ²	Tillers/plant	Panicles/m ²	Grain yield ^b (t/ha)
Chhomro local	46.6 ± 3.27	7.0 ± 1.05	256.6 ± 34.71	4.798 ± 0.475
Raksali local	29.4 ± 4.48	5.6 ± 0.70	263.3 ± 52.30	2.359 ± 0.794
Difference (P = 0.05)	17.2 ns	1.4 ns	6.7 ns	2.439***

^a Yields were estimated from 1 m² crop cuts (n = 10) from seed multiplication block. ^b At 12% moisture content.

No injuries from cold temperatures were observed in traditional varieties Chhomro and Raksali at the seedling stage; most improved lines had either discolored leaves or stunted yellowish growth. Chhomro and Raksali consistently performed better than the exotic cold-tolerant materials for 2 yr. Spikelet sterility on exotic lines was

large (25–100%); no sterility was noticed in Chhomro (Table 1). Yields of Chhomro were significantly superior to those of Raksali in 1986 (Table 2). Widely grown Raksali suffered some spikelet sterility and yielded relatively less than Chhomro.

Most of the exotic lines from

NCTRN and IRCTN failed to set grain at Lumle. Chhomro yields ranged from 4.8 to 5.3 t/ha under rainfed wetland conditions.

Chhomro's cold tolerance could be utilized in developing suitable cold-tolerant rice varieties for temperate areas of Nepal and elsewhere. □

Low temperature tolerance of traditional Vietnamese varieties

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About 2.5 million ha of rice in Vietnam is subjected to low temperature. In the north, low temperature killed 27,110 ha of rice seedlings in 1976.

The first crop Nov–Jun is subjected to low temperatures Nov–Mar (5.0 to 11.0°C minimum temperature), coupled with low sunshine hours (1.3–4.5 h/d). The most common cold injury symptoms are seedling stunting, leaf wilting or even death, spikelet degeneration, poor grain filling, high sterility, and delayed growth.

We evaluated the cold tolerance of 475 traditional Vietnamese rice varieties from the International Rice Germplasm Center to identify possible donor parents for breeding.

The entries could be grouped into five categories: 1) glutinous (mostly japonica), 2) mountain area, 3) winter rice, 4) wet season rice in the north, and 5) wet season rice in the south (Table 1).

Table 1. Response of Vietnamese rice groups to low temperature at the seedling stage. Hanoi, Vietnam.

Group	Varieties (no.) with cold tolerance at seedling stage		
	Good	Poor	Total
Glutinous	9	28	37
Mountain area	4	30	34
Winter rice (Chiem)	14	77	91
Wet season (north)	0	92	92
Wet season (south)	12	209	221
Total	39	436	475

The mountain and winter varieties include many japonicas. Both north and south wet season varieties are indica types.

Varieties were tested at the seedling stage (10°C for 4 d), panicle initiation (17°C for 15 d), and anthesis (17°C for 10 d). At the seedling stage, 39 entries — many of them winter rice varieties — showed cold hardiness (Table 1). A large number of the varieties used in the mountains did not have cold tolerance at the seedling stage. Some glutinous varieties showed cold tolerance at the seedling stage.

Winter rices usually are divided into six subgroups on the basis of morphological characteristics. The Tep group had the highest number of cold-tolerant varieties (Table 2).

The rice plant is most sensitive to low temperature at meiosis or panicle initiation. The outstanding Vietnam entry tolerant of 17°C air temperature at panicle initiation was Bong Sen (Acc. 10861) with a score of 1; Tep Trang and Ba Ren were relatively tolerant at

Table 2. Winter season Vietnam varieties (Chiem) and their response to low temperature at the seedling stage. Hanoi, Vietnam.

Group	Varieties (no.) with indicated cold tolerance		
	Good	Poor	Total
Te (nonglutinous rice)	3	4	7
Tep (fine, short grain)	4	5	9
Cut (round grain)	0	6	6
Bau (large grain)	2	10	12
Saiduong (brown glume)	3	3	6
Other Chiem varieties	29	23	52

panicle initiation and at the seedling stage.

Most of the varieties had relatively poor tolerance at anthesis. The most tolerant are Bong Sen, Nep Da, Nep Den (Acc. 24149), Bat Goat (Acc. 24193), Ba Ren, Tep 62, and Khau Mua Venh.

Ba Ren and Tep 62 are the most promising. Scores for the other Vietnamese varieties are available from the IRGC data bank. □

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization HYBRID RICE

Potassium nutrition in hybrid rice

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We studied hybrid rice Vu 35 at different K levels on a Quaternary red clay soil with pH 6.0, 2.76% organic matter, 70 ppm available K, 240 ppm

slowly available K, and 0.188% N. Conventional variety Xiang 9 was the check.

KC1 was applied at 0, 110, 220, and 440 kg/ha in main plots with 350 kg urea and 550 kg superphosphate/ha. All the P, 2/3 N, and 1/3 K were applied before transplanting, 1/3 N and 2/3 K at tillering. The 2 varieties were transplanted in 4- × 8-m subplots with 3